

**Open Research Case Study
Lancaster University**

Widening Access Through Open Research: The Library Schools Engagement Project

**Charlotte Ross – 4th Year Medical Student - Lancaster Medical School,
Library Schools Engagement Ambassador – Lancaster University Library**

Sophie Holmes - Library Teaching and Engagement Coordinator - Lancaster University Library

**Paul Newnham – Faculty Librarian, Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences - Lancaster University
Library**

Introduction

The Lancaster University Library Schools Engagement Project, established in 2022, is a library-led outreach initiative supporting school and college students, particularly those from Widening Participation (WP) backgrounds across the North West to develop information literacy skills and access academic research for their EPQ (Extended Project Qualification), A-level and BTEC coursework. Initially, the project combined in-school sessions on literature searching with on-campus visits, where students used the library's catalogue, OneSearch, to find relevant resources. The delivery has now shifted to a primarily campus-based model: students receive preparatory materials in advance and then visit the university library to access resources, build independent research skills, and gain insight into higher education. The first year led to a formal evaluation report of the project's impact on information literacy, WP, and academic transition, and the findings have been incorporated into the wider work of the library's schools' team, who accommodate 20 plus schools annually (1).

Open Research Practices Used

A central open research practice within the project is enabling equitable access to academic resources. During on-campus visits, students are given temporary Lancaster logins to access subscription-only materials and are taught to use OneSearch to identify open access resources, ensuring continued access beyond their visit.

The project also incorporates open educational practices, providing handouts and guidance for both students and school staff on literature searching, evaluation, and referencing to support independent study (2). A participatory approach is embedded through having Library School Engagement Ambassadors, Lancaster university students from WP backgrounds, who offer peer support for the students, lead tours, and share insights into university life, helping to demystify higher education.

Rationale and Motivations

The project was driven by the need to address structural inequalities in access to academic knowledge. Many participating schools are from WP backgrounds and have limited library provision, with some offering minimal resources and no access to subscription databases. As a result, students, particularly those completing EPQs, often struggle to find relevant academic literature, especially when researching niche topics. EPQs are typically undertaken alongside 3 or 4 full A-level or BTEC equivalents, contributing to high dropout rates. Therefore, targeted support through this project has helped mitigate some of the reasons why students drop out of doing the EPQ by improving access to resources and providing research skills.

Outcomes and Impact

The project has improved access to high-quality academic literature while equipping students with open access skills to continue research independently. It has also increased confidence and aspiration, with many students gaining their first insight into university life and engaging further through open days or library membership. High levels of repeat school participation and positive feedback highlight its impact, while student ambassadors also benefit through developing employability and peer-support skills.

However, challenges remain. Limited funding has reduced outreach capacity and restricted promotion of the project, meaning many schools are unaware of the project. Travel costs also pose a barrier, particularly for schools located further away leading to some schools being unable to visit the library. While temporary logins provide valuable access during visits, this is short-term; although mitigated through teaching open access strategies, structural barriers to information access persist.

Lessons Learned

This project highlights that access to literature alone is insufficient without the skills to use it effectively; combining resource access with structured information literacy teaching is key to meaningful impact. Embedding open access training ensures benefits extend beyond the university, supporting sustained and equitable engagement with research. The value of peer-led support was also evident, with the Ambassadors playing a crucial role in building confidence and relatability for WP students. However, the shift to a campus-based model demonstrated that accessibility is also shaped by practical factors such as funding, travel, and awareness, which can unintentionally limit reach. Strong partnerships with schools and repeat engagement have helped mitigate this, but the project underscores the need for sustainable funding and wider promotion to maximise impact.

References

1. Newnham, P. and Shaikh, C. (2025) 'Lancaster University Library Schools Engagement', *Journal of Information Literacy*, 19(1), pp. 69–82. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.11645/19.1.645>.
2. Lancaster University Library (2026) *Schools and Colleges*. Available at: <https://lancaster.libguides.com/schools/colleges> (Accessed: 9 April 2026).